

Original Research

Working Capital Management: A Catalyst for Profitability in Bangladesh's Textile Sector

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of working capital management (WCM) on the profitability of firms in Bangladesh's textile sector. Utilizing panel data from 21 publicly listed textile companies over the period 2017–2021, the research examines the relationship between key WCM components, inventory turnover, accounts receivable, accounts payable, and the cash conversion cycle (CCC) and firm profitability, measured by return on assets (ROA). The empirical findings reveal a statistically significant negative correlation between ROA and both the inventory conversion period and the CCC, underscoring the critical role of efficient inventory management and working capital efficiency in enhancing profitability. Furthermore, firm size exhibits a positive association with ROA, suggesting the benefits of economies of scale. In contrast, variables such as receivables, payables, and liquidity ratios demonstrate no significant influence on profitability. The study provides valuable insights for corporate managers and policymakers, emphasizing the importance of optimizing inventory management and leveraging firm size to improve financial performance. These findings contribute to the broader discourse on operational efficiency and have strategic implications for fostering sustainable growth in Bangladesh's textile industry.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Profitability, Working capital management, Textile Industry.

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Introduction

Working capital management (WCM) is crucial for businesses to maintain financial stability and operate efficiently (Ahmad et al., 2022; Alvarez et al., 2021). It represents a major component of a company's overall financial management (Amarasekara et al., 2021). Moreover, WCM plays a critical role in determining a company's performance (Hung & Su Dinh, 2022). In accounting, WCM refers to the process of balancing a company's short-term assets and liabilities to ensure financial health (Asaduzzaman & Chowdhury, 2014). It involves the careful planning and management of current assets and liabilities to minimize the risk of insolvency when meeting short-term obligations, while also avoiding excessive investments in current assets (Eljelly, 2004). Effective working capital management is essential for achieving both liquidity and profitability. Poor management of working capital can result in idle assets, which in turn undermine a company's liquidity and profitability (Banerjee & Deb, 2023). Additionally, WCM significantly impacts various factors, including a company's financial health, industry practices, business size, anticipated sales growth, the proportion of external board members, executive compensation (current portion), and CEO share ownership (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022). Therefore, a thorough understanding of working capital management and the factors influencing it can help businesses mitigate risks and improve overall performance (Nazir & Afza, 2009; Lamberson, 1995). Ultimately, a company's ability to survive depends heavily on its effectiveness in managing cash and current assets.

The textile industry in Bangladesh is a vital pillar of the national economy, contributing approximately 12% to the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and providing employment to around 5 million people (Kiron, 2023). Dominated by the ready-made garments (RMG) segment, the sector generates a substantial portion of Bangladesh's export earnings. However, industry's profitability is challenged by both internal and external factors, including volatile raw material prices, shifting consumer preferences, and intense global competition (Wing, 2020). In this context, working capital management, which involves managing a firm's short-term assets and liabilities to ensure liquidity and uninterrupted operations, plays a critical role. For Bangladeshi textile firms, where operations are capital-intensive, production cycles are long, and dependence on raw materials and exports is high, effective WCM is essential for sustaining profitability and competitiveness (Jahan et al., 2021). The sector's reliance on credit sales, extended production timelines, and substantial inventory levels underscores the importance of efficiently managing key components of working capital, such as inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable. Inefficient WCM can result in liquidity shortages, operational disruptions, and reduced profitability (Ahmed et al., 2017), while optimizing the cash conversion cycle and achieving the right balance between liquidity and profitability can significantly improve a firm's overall performance (Karim et al., 2024).

Optimizing working capital management (WCM) is vital in the textile industry, enabling companies to maintain an optimal balance between profitability and liquidity. By adeptly managing inventory, receivables, and payables, textile firms can significantly enhance cash flow and reduce their dependence on costly external funding (Karim et al., 2024). Central to this is efficiently managing the cash conversion cycle, minimizing the time between purchasing raw materials and receiving payment for finished goods, which

directly boosts operational efficiency and profitability (Jahan et al., 2021). This efficiency becomes particularly critical in the competitive global textile market, known for its often-thin profit margins. In contexts like Bangladesh's textile industry, characterized by extended credit terms, high working capital needs, and lengthy operating cycles covering sourcing to distribution, strong WCM offers a distinct advantage. Companies managing these elements effectively can lower financing costs, prevent liquidity shortages, and improve their return on assets (Ahmed et al., 2017), whereas inefficient WCM often results in detrimental issues like overstocking, delayed customer payments, and excessive reliance on short-term borrowing, ultimately damaging profitability.

The textile industry in Bangladesh struggles with financial and operational challenges that hurt profitability, particularly in managing working capital, a key factor for maintaining liquidity and operational efficiency. Due to long production cycles, high inventory costs, and delayed payments from buyers, textile companies often face cash flow problems, which can hurt their financial health if not managed well. However, despite its importance, there's little research on how working capital management (WCM) affects profitability in Bangladesh's textile sector, creating a gap in the literature. Most existing studies focus on developed economies, with limited attention to emerging markets like Bangladesh (Hossain, 2020). Consequently, understanding how WCM affects the profitability of publicly listed textile companies in Bangladesh is critically important.

The primary objective of this research is to accurately assess the impact of working capital management on the profitability of selected publicly traded textile companies in Bangladesh. More specifically, the study delves into how the efficient management of key working capital components, including inventory, accounts receivable, accounts payable, and the cash conversion cycle, influences the profitability outcomes of these firms. The subsequent sections of this paper are structured as follows: Section 2 provides a review of relevant literature and outlines the study's hypotheses, Section 3 details the research methodology employed, Section 4 presents and discusses the findings, and the final section offers the conclusion.

Literature Survey and Hypothesis Formation

Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) and Profitability

The Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) measures how long a company takes to sell its inventory, including the time needed to turn raw materials into finished goods (Obeidat, 2021). A shorter ICP indicates efficient inventory management, leading to faster sales, lower storage costs, and better cash flow. In contrast, a longer ICP suggests inefficiency, tying up capital, increasing storage expenses, raising obsolescence risks, and hurting profitability (Lin & Wang, 2021). Inventory management involves three stages: converting raw materials into products, time spent in production, and holding finished goods before sale (Fabozzi & Peterson, 2003). Industries like textiles, with fast-changing trends and complex production, must optimize ICP to stay profitable (Garg & Meentu, 2022). Effective inventory control boosts profits, while delays lead to higher costs and lost sales (Hossain, 2020).

Most research finds a negative link between ICP and profitability; shorter ICP means higher profits due to efficient inventory handling (Mazumder, 2023; Banerjee & Deb, 2023; Garg & Meentou, 2022; Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Obeidat, 2021; Amarasekara et al., 2021; Farooq, 2019; Muturi et al., 2015; Mansoori & Muhammad, 2012; Falope & Ajilore, 2009, and Lazaridis & Tryfonidis, 2006). However, some studies (e.g., Gill et al., 2010; Mathuva, 2010) argue that a longer ICP can sometimes increase profits if firms stockpile inventory to meet sudden demand or secure bulk discounts. These differences likely stem from industry, regional, or company-specific factors.

In Bangladesh's textile sector, where competition is fierce, demand fluctuates, and inventory practices vary (Chowdhury et al., 2024), ICP management is especially critical. Reliance on imported materials and shifting fashion trends make inventory control challenging (Khan et al., 2020). Thus, analyzing how ICP affects profitability in this unique context is vital.

H₁: There is an inverse relationship between the Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) and profitability (ROA), indicating that companies with longer ICPs tend to have lower profitability.

Accounts Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP) and Profitability

Accounts Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP) measures how long a company takes to collect payments from customers after making sales (Lazarus et al., 2023). Also called the debtor's conversion period, it reflects a firm's credit policy effectiveness. While offering credit can boost sales and profits, inefficient collection processes may erase these benefits through higher administrative costs (Eljelly, 2004).

A long ARCP hurts profitability in several ways, such as delayed cash inflows reducing funds for operations and investments, limiting the ability to pay short-term debts, or seizing growth opportunities (Mathuva, 2010). May cause companies to miss early payment discounts (Banerjee & Deb, 2023). Conversely, a short ARCP indicates strong credit management, improving liquidity, and working capital efficiency (Lazaridis & Tryfonidis, 2006).

Most research confirms this negative ARCP-profitability relationship across industries, including textiles (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Amarasekara et al., 2021; Mansoori & Muhammad, 2012; Falope & Ajilore, 2009; Garcia-Teruel & Martinez-Solano, 2007; Raheman & Nasr, 2007). However, some studies show that flexible credit terms can increase sales and strengthen customer ties, potentially improving profits (Box et al., 2017; Kung'u et al., 2014). This suggests the relationship depends on industry context and credit management approaches.

For Bangladesh's textile sector, where credit sales are standard practice, maintaining a shorter ARCP appears crucial for ensuring adequate working capital, minimizing bad debt risks, and optimizing cash conversion cycles (Uddin et al., 2023; Mazumder, 2023).

H₂: A significant negative relationship exists between ARCP and profitability in Bangladesh's publicly traded textile companies.

Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP) and Profitability

The Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP) refers to the time a company takes to settle its obligations to suppliers. A longer APCP enables firms to hold onto cash for extended periods, thereby improving liquidity and allowing greater flexibility in allocating resources toward investments or operational needs (Deloof, 2003). Efficient management of payables can also reduce reliance on external financing, which in turn may enhance profitability (Lazaridis & Tryfonidis, 2006). However, while extending the APCP may offer liquidity advantages, excessive delays in supplier payments can negatively impact supplier relationships, lead to the forfeiture of early payment discounts, and damage a firm's reputation (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022). As such, firms must carefully balance the benefits of delayed payments against the potential risks to supply chain efficiency. Effective APCP management can significantly influence a company's liquidity, cash flow, and overall profitability (Hamad, 2024).

Existing research showed mixed findings. Empirical studies, including those by Hamad (2024), Srour & Azmy (2021), Aryawan & Indriani (2020), and Mathuva (2010), have identified a positive association between APCP and profitability, suggesting that longer payment periods may improve profitability by preserving working capital. Conversely, other researchers such as Tweresh (2024), Ruguru (2023), Ray (2012), Mekonnen (2011), Raheman & Nasr (2007), Vural et al. (2012), and Saghir et al. (2011) report that firms with lower profitability often delay payments due to underlying cash flow challenges.

In the context of the Bangladeshi textile industry, where supplier credit terms play a crucial role in working capital management, efficient handling of APCP is essential (Uddin et al., 2023; Mazumder, 2023). Firms that can strategically extend their APCP without straining supplier relationships are better positioned to enhance profitability by optimizing cash flow and reducing financial pressure.

H₃: Publicly listed Bangladeshi textile companies with longer APCP demonstrate higher profitability.

Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) and Profitability

The Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) measures how efficiently a company manages its working capital by tracking how quickly investments convert into cash (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022). Calculated as $(ICP + ARCP) - APCP$ (Azam & Haider, 2011; Deloof, 2003), a shorter CCC signals better working capital management, companies recover their investments faster, improving liquidity and potentially increasing profits.

Most research confirms a clear negative relationship between CCC and profitability. Studies from Deloof (2003) to recent work by Hung & Dinh (2022) show that firms with shorter cycles manage inventory, receivables, and payables more effectively. This reduces reliance on external financing and boosts financial performance. Numerous other researchers (Deari & Palomba, 2024; Kukeli et al., 2024; Kavyashree, 2024; Rahman & Ahmed, 2021; Ahmed et al., 2017; Azam & Haider, 2011; Mansoori & Muhammad, 2012; Mekonnen, 2011; Ray, 2012; Vural et al., 2012; Saghir et al., 2011; Velnampy &

Niresh, 2012; Shin & Soenen, 1998) consistently find that efficient working capital management (shorter CCC) leads to higher profitability.

However, few studies reveal important exceptions. Over-optimizing the CCC might hurt profits by causing inventory shortages or damaging supplier relations (Mekonnen, 2011; Ray, 2012). This suggests a potential liquidity-profitability trade-off, particularly relevant in high-risk industries like textiles. Additionally, most studies don't account for Bangladesh's unique textile industry conditions that may alter how CCC affects profitability.

Bangladesh's textile sector faces special challenges such as fierce competition, thin margins, and extreme reliance on cash flow efficiency (Moin et al., 2024; Jewel et al., 2022). Factors like export dependence, volatile material costs, and labor intensity make CCC management particularly crucial here. Understanding these industry-specific dynamics is essential for accurately assessing CCC's impact on profitability in this context.

H4: Textile companies listed in Bangladesh show significantly lower profitability as their Cash Conversion Cycle lengthens.

The Current Ratio (CR) or Liquidity and Profitability

The Current Ratio (CR) measures a company's ability to pay short-term debts using short-term assets (Olaoye et al., 2019). Calculated as current assets divided by current liabilities, a higher CR typically indicates stronger liquidity and better capacity to meet obligations (Akoto et al., 2013). However, financial managers face the ongoing challenge of balancing liquidity with profitability (Eljelly, 2004).

While high liquidity reduces insolvency risk, excessive liquidity can be inefficient. It may indicate underutilized resources sitting idle rather than being invested profitably (Islam et al., 2022). Multiple studies confirm this inverse relationship between CR and profitability (Al-Mamun et al., 2018; Ahmed et al., 2017; Asaduzzaman & Chowdhury, 2014; Singhania et al., 2014).

Most research strongly supports this negative correlation. Studies across different markets consistently show that companies maintaining very high liquidity tend to achieve lower profitability (Islam et al., 2022; Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Olaoye et al., 2019; Rahman & Nasr, 2007). This suggests that over-investment in current assets often comes at the expense of more profitable opportunities. However, the relationship isn't absolute. Some findings reveal important nuances, such as high liquidity protects against market volatility, especially crucial in textiles (Jahan et al., 2021). An optimal middle ground exists where neither extreme liquidity nor extreme leanness maximizes profits.

For Bangladesh's textile industry, this balance is particularly critical (Farhana et al., 2022). The sector's working-capital-intensive nature demands sufficient liquidity for operations (Rahman & Raju, 2022), yet excessive liquidity ties up funds that could generate higher returns (Jahan et al., 2021). This highlights the need for context-specific liquidity management strategies.

Hypothesis 5 (H₅): Listed Bangladeshi textile companies with higher Current Ratios demonstrate lower profitability.

Firm Size (FS) and Profitability

The relationship between firm size and profitability has been widely studied, with researchers highlighting that size influences a company's ability to achieve economies of scale, negotiate better supplier terms, secure favorable financing, and strengthen market competitiveness (Hung & Dinh, 2022). Larger firms typically benefit from diversified product lines, greater bargaining power, and financial capacity to invest in advanced technology, which can boost profitability (Olaoye et al., 2019). However, excessive growth can lead to diseconomies of scale, inefficiencies, and bureaucratic inertia, negatively affecting profitability (Lee, 2009).

Empirical evidence on this relationship remains inconclusive. Some studies (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Sudiyatno et al., 2020; Pervan & Višić, 2012; Singla, 2011; Raheman & Nasr, 2007; Deloof, 2003) report a positive correlation, while others suggest a more complex, non-linear pattern. Lee (2009) found that while larger firms initially gain higher profitability due to cost advantages and market power, these benefits diminish as firms grow excessively, leading to operational inefficiencies.

Conversely, some research indicates that smaller firms may achieve higher profitability through agility, innovation, and adaptability (Hapsari & Amalia, 2023; Marlina & Arisudhana, 2022). In Bangladesh, larger firms' advantages in financing and fixed-cost distribution do not always guarantee superior profitability if inefficiencies arise from excessive scale (Chowdhury et al., 2021).

Bangladesh's textile industry includes small family-owned businesses and large conglomerates, with firm size significantly influencing profitability (Jewel et al., 2022). Larger textile firms often benefit from economies of scale in production, marketing, and distribution, improving profitability. They also have better access to capital for expansion and innovation (Serrasqueiro & Nunes, 2008). In contrast, smaller firms may struggle with financing, production efficiency, and cost competitiveness, potentially reducing profitability (Ima et al., 2024). However, their flexibility and responsiveness to market changes can provide niche advantages.

These mixed findings suggest that the firm size-profitability relationship depends on industry-specific factors, operational scale, and financial structure. Given the unique dynamics of Bangladesh's textile sector, a closer examination is warranted.

H₆: A significant relationship exists between Firm Size (FS) and the profitability of listed textile companies in Bangladesh.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methodology

The study employed quantitative research methods. This approach centers on measuring and analyzing data numerically. It is based on a deductive methodology, rooted in positivist and empiricist philosophies, which prioritizes the testing of theories (Bryman, 2012).

Sample and Data

The study's population comprises all Bangladeshi textile manufacturing companies. The target populations of this study consist of Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) listed textile manufacturing companies in Bangladesh. There are fifty-eight textile manufacturing companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE), out of which twenty-one (37% of the target population) textile manufacturing companies were selected based on the availability of required data for the period from 2016-17 to 2020-21. An overview of the sample inclusion criteria is as follows.

Total Listed Textile Companies on the DSE	54
Less: Annual Report not found on the company website for the study period of 2016-17 to 2020-21	(21)
Less: Required information (considered for the study) not found in the annual reports	(16)
Final selected textile companies	21

This study is based on secondary data collected from the annual reports of 21 selected textile companies listed on the DSE, covering the fiscal years 2016-17 to 2020-21. With five years of data from each company, the sample size consists of 105 observations (21*5). The annual reports of all selected textile companies are publicly available on the DSE website. As independent auditors audit these reports, they are considered transparent and trustworthy. Furthermore, the data were cross-verified for accuracy whenever feasible.

Measurement of Variables

Dependent Variable

Dependent variables are outcomes influenced by independent variables and other external conditions. In this study, Return on Assets (ROA) serves as the dependent variable, measuring the financial performance of selected textile firms. ROA is a profitability ratio that indicates how efficiently a company generates earnings from its total assets (Atidhira & Yustina, 2019). A higher ROA reflects superior asset utilization and greater profitability, all else being equal (Idawati & Wahyudi, 2015). ROA is widely used in financial research as a key profitability metric. Prior studies employing ROA include Kiyamaz et al. (2024), Hassan et al. (2023), Itan & Angellina (2023), Ahmad et al. (2022), Banerjee & Deb (2023), Habib & Kayani (2022), Lin & Wang (2021), Garg & Meentu (2022), Alvarez et al. (2021), Jahan et al. (2021), Amarasekara et al. (2021), Nazir & Afza (2009), Karim et al. (2018), and Raheman & Nasr (2007).

Independent Variables

An independent variable can have either a positive or a negative effect on the dependent variable. In this study, four key independent variables were used to assess the impact of working capital management on the profitability of Bangladeshi textile firms: Account Payable Conversion Period (APCP), Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC), Account Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP), and Inventory Conversion Period (ICP). These variables serve as efficient indicators, measuring how effectively a company manages its working capital. Firms can analyze these metrics to evaluate their liquidity management, operational efficiency, and overall financial health.

Inventory Conversion Period (ICP)

Inventory management involves strategies to optimize stock levels, enhancing profitability and competitiveness. An efficient system ensures: Adequate supply of raw materials during shortages and price fluctuations, Uninterrupted production, Minimized carrying costs and storage time, and Optimal inventory investment (Deloof, 2003). A key metric in working capital management is the Inventory Conversion Period (ICP), or inventory turnover in days, which measures how quickly a firm converts stock into sales (Rahman, 2011). It is calculated as: Average inventory/ cost of goods sold per day. This ratio indicates inventory management efficiency. Prior research (Kiyamaz et al., 2024; Hassan et al., 2023; Ahmad et al., 2022; Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Alvarez et al., 2021; Amarasekara et al., 2021) has used ICP as an independent variable to assess working capital management (WCM).

Accounts Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP)

The Accounts Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP) measures how long a company takes to collect payments from customers after making credit sales (Lazarus et al., 2023). Calculated as: $ARCP = (\text{Accounts Receivable} / \text{Net Credit Sales}) \times \text{Number of Days}$. This metric is a critical component of the cash conversion cycle and significantly impacts both liquidity and profitability (Uyar, 2009; Lazaridis & Tryfonidis, 2006). Effective ARCP

management is particularly crucial for cash flow and profitability in industries like textiles, where credit sales dominate transactions (Amarasekara et al., 2021). For this study, ARCP serves as an independent variable influencing the profitability of Bangladesh's listed textile companies. Existing research consistently shows a significant relationship between ARCP and corporate profitability (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Amarasekara et al., 2021; Rahaman et al., 2021; Raheman & Nasr, 2007).

Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP)

The Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP) or Payables Deferral Period represents the average time a company takes to pay suppliers after receiving goods/services (Lin & Wang, 2021), calculated as $(\text{Accounts Payable}/\text{Net Purchases}) \times \text{Number of Days}$. As a critical working capital management component, APCP significantly affects cash flow and liquidity (Kiymaz et al., 2024). While extended APCP improves free cash flow by effectively using suppliers as a financing source, excessively delayed payments may damage supplier relationships and credit terms. Research consistently demonstrates APCP's substantial influence on profitability (Itan & Angellina, 2023; Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Amarasekara et al., 2021; Rahaman et al., 2021; Eljelly, 2004; Deloof, 2003), highlighting its strategic importance in financial management.

Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC)

The Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) is a crucial metric for assessing working capital management efficiency (Alvarez et al., 2021), measuring how long a company takes to convert inventory investments into cash from sales (Lazaridis & Tryfonidis, 2006). Calculated as $\text{CCC} = \text{Inventory Conversion Period} + \text{Accounts Receivable Conversion Period} - \text{Accounts Payable Conversion Period}$, it reflects operational effectiveness: a shorter cycle indicates efficient capital use and potentially higher profitability, while a longer cycle suggests inefficiencies in managing inventory, receivables, or payables that may impair cash flow (Deloof, 2003). Numerous studies have employed CCC as an independent variable to analyze working capital management's impact on profitability (Kiymaz et al., 2024; Hassan et al., 2023; Ahmad et al., 2022; Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Alvarez et al., 2021; Amarasekara et al., 2021).

Control Variables

Control variables, while not central to the research question, may affect the dependent variable (Bhandari, 2021; Mehta, 2015). This study includes Current Ratio (CR) and Firm Size (FS) as control variables since these fundamental firm characteristics could influence profitability alongside the primary independent variables.

Current Ratio (CR)

The Current Ratio (CR), calculated as Current Assets divided by Current Liabilities, is a fundamental liquidity measure assessing a firm's ability to cover short-term obligations (Bashir et al., 2013; Amal et al., 2012). While a higher CR typically indicates stronger liquidity, its effect on profitability hinges on the efficiency of current asset management - excessive liquidity may reflect suboptimal capital allocation. Given its

critical role in financial stability, CR has been consistently used as a control variable in working capital-profitability studies (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Amarasekara et al., 2021), with numerous researchers confirming its analytical relevance (Hassan et al., 2023; Ahmad et al., 2022; Islam et al., 2022; Al-Mamun et al., 2018). This study accordingly incorporates CR to maintain methodological consistency with established literature.

Firm Size (FS)

Firm size (FS), typically measured as the natural logarithm of total sales ($FS = \text{Log of Total Sales}$), is a critical factor in examining working capital management's impact on profitability (Amal et al., 2012; Theiri & Abdessatar, 2011; Bashir et al., 2013). Larger firms enjoy distinct advantages, including economies of scale, superior access to capital markets, and enhanced supplier bargaining power, all of which significantly influence working capital policies and profitability outcomes (Gill & Mathur, 2010). Research demonstrates that larger firms possess greater working capital management flexibility, which often translates to higher profitability (Sharma & Kumar, 2011) while also substantially affecting liquidity requirements and working capital needs (Lazaridis & Tryfonidis, 2006). Consequently, FS has been consistently employed as a control variable in studies analyzing working capital management's profitability effects (Kiymaz et al., 2024; Hassan et al., 2023; Ahmad et al., 2022; Alvarez et al., 2021).

Bangladesh's textile sector operates within a unique competitive landscape shaped by regulatory policies, technological adoption, and market positioning, leading to varying working capital management (WCM) efficiencies across firms. While macroeconomic factors like inflation, interest rates, exchange rates, and GDP growth demonstrably affect profitability (ROA) through their impact on cash conversion cycles, this study deliberately focuses on the direct relationship between WCM components and ROA.

This study focuses exclusively on firm-level financial metrics for three key reasons: First, since working capital management (WCM) is inherently an internal financial process, excluding industry and macroeconomic factors allows for direct analysis of its relationship with profitability. Second, macroeconomic data often suffers from availability and consistency issues, while firm-specific financial data ensures standardized comparability across all sampled companies. Third, methodological considerations preclude including multiple external variables, particularly macroeconomic indicators like inflation and GDP growth, to avoid multicollinearity and maintain model clarity; consequently, the analysis is limited to the most relevant controls (current ratio and firm size) for precise interpretation of WCM's impact. This focused approach ensures the analysis remains interpretable while directly testing WCM's impact on profitability.

Table 1: Summary of Variables and Measurement

Variables	Abbreviation	Measurement
Return on Assets	ROA	$\frac{\text{Profit before interest and Tax}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
Inventory Conversion Period	ICP	$\frac{\text{Average Inventory}}{\text{Net Sales}} \times 365$
Account Receivable Conversion Period	ARCP	$\frac{\text{Average Account Recivable}}{\text{Net Sales}} \times 365$
Account Payable Conversion Period	APCP	$\frac{\text{Average Account Payable}}{\text{Net Purchase}} \times 365$
Cash Conversion Cycle	CCC	Accounts receivable period + inventory conversion period - accounts payable period
Current Ratio	CR	$\frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$
Firms Size	FS	Natural log of sales

Data Analysis

This study employed a comprehensive statistical analysis to examine the data. First, descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, minimums, and maximums) were calculated for all variables, including profitability measures, working capital components, and control variables. Second, Pearson correlation analysis identified the strength and direction of relationships between working capital management variables and profitability. Third, a multiple linear regression model assessed working capital management's impact on profitability while controlling for other influential factors. All analyses were performed using SPSS (Version 29.0.2.0) to ensure methodological rigor.

Regression Model:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ICP_{it}) + \beta_2(ARCP_{it}) + \beta_3(APCP_{it}) + \beta_4(CCC_{it}) + \beta_5(CR_{it}) + \beta_6(SF_{it}) + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Were,

ROA_{it} = Return on Assets of Firm i at time t, ($i = 1, 2 \dots 42$ firms & $t = 1.2 \dots 12$ years)

ICP = Inventory Conversion Period,

$ARPC$ = Account Receivable Conversion Period,

$APCP$ = Account Payable Conversion Period,

CCC = Cash Conversion Cycle,

CR = Current Ratio,

SF = Size of the Firm,

β_0 = Constant Term,

β_1 = coefficients.

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Analysis

Table 2 summarizes the key financial metrics for 105 textile companies in Bangladesh from 2017 to 2021. It shows average performance across six critical areas: (1) inventory management, (2) customer payments, (3) supplier payments, (4) liquidity, (5) profitability, and (6) company size. The table presents the mean, standard deviation, and range for each variable, giving a comprehensive picture of working capital efficiency in the sector.

The following analysis reveals significant variations in working capital management among Bangladeshi textile firms. On average, companies take 190.08 days (SD=178.37) to convert inventory into sales, with extreme values ranging from 25.50 to 831.34 days, indicating substantial differences in inventory management efficiency. This aligns with findings by Lazaridis & Tryfonidis (2006) for inventory-intensive industries.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) [Days]	25.50	831.34	190.08	178.37
Account Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP) [Days]	6.11	448.87	149.98	96.87
Account Payable Conversion Period (APCP) [Days]	2.70	191.89	56.77	63.00
Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) [Days]	-64.25	1269.23	283.29	270.01
Return on Assets (ROA) [%]	-0.03	0.09	0.05	0.03
Current Ratio (CR) [:]	0.58	10.81	2.06	2.13
Firm Size (FS) [Log of Sales]	2.20	4.04	3.31	0.53
N=105				

Firms require an average of 149.98 days (SD=96.87) to collect receivables, considerably longer than the 44-day average reported by Lazarus et al. (2023) in Ghana. The accounts payable cycle averages 56.77 days (SD=63.00), suggesting varying supplier payment strategies. These factors contribute to an extended cash conversion cycle (CCC) averaging 283.29 days (SD=270.01) - significantly higher than the 204-day average found by Karim et al. (2024) for Bangladeshi manufacturers.

Profitability metrics show modest performance, with ROA averaging 5% (SD=3%), comparable to Lazaridis & Tryfonidis's (2006) findings. Liquidity positions vary widely (CR=2.06±2.13), while firm size distribution (log sales=3.31±0.53) confirms sample diversity.

The study shows that Bangladesh's textile companies have more inconsistent working capital management (WCM) practices compared to both other local industries (Hossain, 2020) and international manufacturers (Lazarus et al., 2023; Sawarni et al., 2021; Obeidat, 2021). Two key problem areas stand out: companies take too long to collect customer payments (ARCP) and have inefficient cash conversion cycles (CCC) when measured

against global standards (Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Sawarni et al., 2021). While the sector's profitability matches historical trends, the big differences in how companies manage inventory (ICP) and maintain cash reserves (CR) lead to clear opportunities for better operations. Some firms do show smart cash flow management with negative CCC values. Overall, these results highlight an important gap: Bangladesh's textile industry needs more consistent WCM approaches to compete effectively, as the current mix of strong and weak practices creates both risks and advantages for different companies.

Correlation Analysis

The correlation matrix presents the interrelationships between key financial metrics in Bangladesh's textile sector, including: (1) working capital management components, Inventory Conversion Period (ICP), Accounts Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP), Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP), and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC); (2) liquidity measure (Current Ratio, CR); (3) firm size (FS); and (4) profitability indicator (Return on Assets, ROA). This analysis reveals how these critical financial variables interact within the industry.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

	ICP	ARCP	APCP	CCC	CR	FS	ROA
ICP	1						
ARCP	.573**	1					
APCP	-.233	-.221	1				
CCC	.921**	.789**	-.466*	1			
CR	-.135	.204	-.213	.034	1		
FS	-.575**	-.329	.018	-.502*	-.002	1	
ROA	-.728**	-.290	-.057	-.571**	.427	.611**	1

** (p< 0.01); * 5% (p<0.05); n=105

The results reveal a strong negative correlation between Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) and profitability (ROA) ($r = -0.728$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that prolonged inventory turnover significantly reduces profitability—consistent with prior research (Hung & Dinh, 2022; Alvarez et al., 2021; Deloof, 2003). Similarly, the Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) shows a significant negative relationship with ROA ($r = -0.571$, $p < 0.001$), reinforcing that firms with faster cash cycles achieve higher profitability (Olaoye et al., 2019; Lin & Wang, 2021).

In contrast, Accounts Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP) and Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP) exhibit weak, statistically insignificant correlations with ROA ($r = -0.290$ and $r = -0.057$, respectively). The lack of significance for ARCP contrasts with findings in SMEs (Garcia-Teruel & Solano, 2007), possibly due to sector-specific dynamics in Bangladesh. The APCP result also diverges from Lazaridis & Tryfonidis (2006), suggesting that delayed supplier payments may not enhance profitability in this context.

Liquidity (CR) shows a moderate positive but insignificant link to ROA ($r = 0.427$), aligning with Eljelly (2004) on liquidity's role in financial health. Firm size (FS) strongly

correlates with profitability ($r = 0.611, p < 0.001$), supporting economies of scale advantages (Amato & Burson, 2007).

The interdependencies among Working Capital Management (WCM) variables reveal that Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) are strongly positively correlated, as are Accounts Receivable Collection Period (ARCP) and CCC, indicating that longer inventory and receivables cycles prolong cash conversion. Conversely, Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP) and CCC show a negative correlation, implying that shorter payment terms reduce CCC. Additionally, firm size moderately decreases ICP (correlation: -0.43), underscoring larger firms' greater efficiency in inventory management. These relationships highlight how optimizing inventory, receivables, and payables collectively influences cash conversion efficiency, especially for Bangladeshi textile companies.

Regression Analysis

This regression analysis examines how working capital management affects the profitability of textile firms in Bangladesh. The results, presented in the following table, include key metrics such as coefficients, significance levels, and goodness-of-fit statistics. These findings help identify which working capital factors, such as inventory, receivables, or payables, have the strongest impact on the financial performance of Bangladeshi textile companies.

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Independent Variables	Dependent Variable Return on Assets (ROA)
Inventory Conversion Period (ICP)	-0.565 (0.008**)
Account Receivable Conversion Period (ARCP)	-0.080 (0.709)
Accounts Payable Conversion Period (APCP)	-0.038 (0.826)
Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC)	-0.344 (0.109)
Current Ratio (CR)	0.427 (0.054*)
Firm Size (FS)	0.611 (0.003**)
R^2	0.619
R^2_{adj}	0.523
F-Statistics	6.489

Table 4 shows that the Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) has a significant negative effect on Return on Assets (ROA), with a coefficient of -0.565 and a p -value of 0.008 (p

< 0.01). This confirms that longer inventory holding periods reduce profitability; each one-unit increase in ICP decreases ROA by 0.565 units, all else being equal. The result supports H1, aligning with prior studies (e.g., Banerjee & Deb (2023); Garg & Meenttu (2022); Jaworski & Czerwonka (2022); Obeidat (2021); Amarasekara et al. (2021); Farooq (2019); Hung & Dinh (2022), Alvarez et al. (2021), and Deloof (2003) and highlights the critical need for efficient inventory management in Bangladesh's textile sector, where excess stock can lead to high holding costs and obsolescence risks.

The Current Ratio (CR) has a positive but marginally significant relationship with ROA (coefficient = 0.427, $p = 0.054$), suggesting that better liquidity may slightly enhance profitability by improving short-term financial flexibility. This validates H5 and is consistent with past research (e.g., Hassan et al., 2023; Islam et al., 2022; Jaworski & Czerwonka, 2022; Olaoye et al., 2019; Al-Mamun et al., 2018; Ahmed et al., 2017; Ahmad et al., 2022; Eljelly, 2004).

Firm Size (FS), measured by log sales, has a strong positive impact on ROA (coefficient = 0.611, $p = 0.003$), confirming H6. Larger firms likely benefit from economies of scale, stronger market presence, and better access to financing, as seen in earlier studies (e.g., Kiyamaz et al., 2024; Hassan et al., 2023; Ahmad et al., 2022; Alvarez et al., 2021; Raheman & Nasr, 2007; Deloof, 2003).

However, Accounts Receivable (ARCP), Accounts Payable (APCP), and Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) show no significant effect on ROA ($p > 0.05$), leading to the rejection of H2, H3, and H4, possibly because CCC and ICP directly influence cash flow efficiency, making them more impactful than ARCP or APCP, and because stable credit terms (ARCP/APCP) in the sector may diminish their effect, whereas inventory management (ICP) remains a critical driver of competitiveness.

The model explains 52.3% (Adjusted R^2) of ROA variation, indicating a strong fit, and the F-statistic confirms overall significance. These findings suggest that optimizing inventory and liquidity, rather than receivables or payables, is crucial for profitability in Bangladesh's textile industry. Larger firms should leverage their scale advantages, while policymakers and managers should prioritize inventory turnover and working capital efficiency.

Conclusion

This research explores the role of working capital management (WCM) as a determinant of profitability within Bangladesh's textile industry, specifically analyzing listed manufacturing enterprises from 2017 to 2021. Working capital, defined as the surplus of current assets over current liabilities used for operational funding, requires effective management (WCM) of these balance sheet items to ensure solvency and drive profitability.

A quantitative methodology was adopted, analyzing secondary data through descriptive statistics to outline variable characteristics (mean, standard deviation, range). Correlation analysis was conducted to evaluate the association between WCM elements

and profitability. Subsequently, regression analysis was employed to probe the predictive relationship between these variables.

Correlation findings suggest that the management of inventory turnover and the cash conversion cycle significantly influence profitability. Specifically, prolonged inventory holding periods (ICP) and extended cash conversion cycles (CCC) were negatively associated with profitability, whereas larger firm size (FS) exhibited a positive correlation. In contrast, the Accounts Receivable Collection Period (ARCP), Accounts Payable Payment Period (APCP), and Current Ratio (CR) demonstrated weak or non-significant relationships with profitability. These results emphasize that efficient WCM practices are crucial for enhancing financial performance in this sector.

Regression analysis further revealed that the Inventory Conversion Period (ICP) and Firm Size (FS) are the most statistically significant predictors of profitability among the variables studied. This indicates that operational scale and the efficiency of inventory management are primary drivers of profitability for Bangladeshi textile firms. Liquidity (Current Ratio) showed a significant borderline impact, while ARCP, APCP, and CCC did not emerge as significant predictors in the regression model.

The findings underscore the pivotal role of working capital management (WCM) in boosting profitability in Bangladesh's textile sector and call for strategic policy actions. Efficient inventory management should be promoted through JIT systems, digital tools, supported by regulatory incentives and R&D investment. Liquidity must be optimized, not maximized, with low-interest loans and tailored banking products to support short-term obligations. As firm size positively affects profitability, policies should enable mergers and enhance export incentives. Improving the Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) is essential, requiring faster receivables collection, strategic payables extension, and adoption of digital payments and supply chain financing tools. Collectively, these interventions will strengthen financial performance, scalability, and global competitiveness in the textile industry.

Concentrating on listed companies and utilizing secondary data, this study confirms the significance of WCM for textile sector profitability. Recommendations for future research include extending the analysis to non-listed entities, investigating different industrial sectors, and employing alternative measures of profitability to further elucidate the WCM-profitability nexus.

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